

Environmental Disclosure and Financial Performance of Oil and Gas Firms in Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined the environmental disclosure and financial performance of oil and gas firms in Nigeria for a period of 10 years 2015-2024. The specific objectives of the study include to: ascertain the effect of environment cost disclosure on net profit margin of oil and gas firms in Nigeria, examine effect of environment cost disclosure on return on assets of oil and gas firms in Nigeria and evaluate effect of environment cost disclosure on asset turnover of oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The study used secondary sources of data from the annual report of the selected listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. Ex-post facto research design was also adopted. The statistical techniques used for this study were descriptive statistics and panel least square regression. The study found out that environment cost disclosure has negative (coefficient - 235.1044) and non-significant (P-value 0.5788 > 0.05) effect on net profit margin of oil and gas firms in Nigeria, environment cost disclosure has a positive (coefficient 29.98939) and non-significant (P-value 0.0002 < 0.05) effect on return on assets of oil and gas firms in Nigeria and environment cost disclosure has a positive (coefficient -0.122778) and non-significant (P-value 0.8694 > 0.05) effect on asset turnover of oil and gas firms in Nigeria. Based on the findings the following recommendation were made: Companies should strive to better integrate environmental initiatives into their core operations to transform them from cost burdens into strategic advantages. Management should explore more cost-effective and sustainable environmental practices, and consider using green innovations that enhance efficiency and minimize waste, potentially improving profitability in the long run, Oil and gas firms should continue and possibly expand their environmental cost disclosures. Transparent and consistent reporting can attract environmentally conscious investors and improve resource management, which enhances asset utilization and long-term performance. Regulatory bodies should also promote mandatory environmental reporting frameworks to further support this positive link and Oil and gas firms should not disregard environmental cost disclosure. Rather, they should focus on improving the efficiency of their assets while maintaining environmental responsibility. This includes investing in eco-efficient technologies that reduce environmental impacts without compromising operational performance, which may help to eventually convert disclosures into tangible efficiency gains

Keywords: Environmental Disclosure; Financial Performance; Oil and Gas Firms; Environmental Cost Disclosure; Assets Utilization; Net Profit Margin

Introduction

The oil and gas industry in Nigeria has been associated with significant environmental challenges such as oil spills, gas flaring, and waste generation, which impose substantial costs on companies and their host communities. In recent years, there has been increasing pressure on firms to disclose their environmental costs and sustainability practices in their annual reports, as stakeholders demand greater accountability and transparency. This demand has been reinforced by regulatory shifts, particularly the Nigerian government's 2024 directive mandating climate- and environment-related disclosures, aimed at aligning local reporting standards with global sustainability frameworks. These requirements not only raise compliance costs but also create

opportunities for firms to enhance their reputational capital and strengthen stakeholder trust (Reuters, 2024; The Guardian, 2024).

Despite these developments, the relationship between environmental cost disclosure and the financial performance of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria remains inconclusive. Some studies report that detailed disclosure of environmental costs positively influences financial indicators such as return on assets, net profit margin, and firm value, while others reveal little or no significant impact. This inconsistency highlights a gap in the literature, particularly in the Nigerian context, where environmental degradation and sustainability issues are pressing concerns. Consequently, this study seeks to evaluate the effect of environmental cost disclosure on the financial performance of listed Nigerian oil and gas firms, providing insights that will guide managers, investors, and regulators in decision-making (Ujah, Soomiyol & Yua, 2025; Sunday, 2024; Anonymous, 2022).

Statement of the Problem

The problem underlying this study stems from the persistent environmental degradation caused by oil and gas operations in Nigeria and the uncertainty about how firms' disclosure of environmental costs influences their financial outcomes. Oil exploration and production have resulted in severe ecological damage, including oil spills, gas flaring, and waste mismanagement, which not only threaten host communities but also impose long-term liabilities on firms. Although regulatory bodies and stakeholders now demand greater transparency through environmental cost disclosure, compliance levels among Nigerian oil and gas firms remain inconsistent, with many companies providing partial or symbolic information. Existing empirical studies on the link between environmental disclosure and financial performance present conflicting results, with some suggesting that such disclosures enhance profitability, corporate value, and investor confidence, while others argue they impose additional costs that may reduce competitiveness. This ambiguity creates a knowledge gap, especially in the Nigerian context where sustainability reporting is still evolving under new government directives. Thus, the central problem is whether environmental cost disclosure genuinely contributes to improving the financial performance of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria or whether it merely represents a regulatory burden with limited economic benefits.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the environmental disclosure and financial performance of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

The specific objectives are to:

- i. Examine the effect of environment cost disclosure on net profit margin of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.
- ii. Evaluate the effect of environment cost disclosure to return on assets of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.
- iii. Ascertain the effect of environment cost disclosure on asset turnover of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

The study will therefore be of great importance to various interest groups:

Regulators and Policymakers: Government agencies such as the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) and the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) will benefit from the findings as they provide evidence-based insights into how environmental disclosure influences corporate financial outcomes. This will help in designing and enforcing more effective policies, sustainability frameworks, and compliance mechanisms that balance environmental accountability with economic growth.

Oil and Gas Firms: The study will guide listed oil and gas companies in understanding whether environmental cost disclosure improves their financial performance or simply adds to their reporting burdens. With this knowledge, firms can adopt more strategic approaches to sustainability reporting, enhance corporate reputation, attract investment, and possibly reduce long-term environmental liabilities.

Scope of the Study

The scope of this study covers an investigation into the environmental disclosure and financial performance of oil and gas firms in Nigeria. In terms of topic scope, the study focuses specifically on the relationship between environmental cost disclosure and key financial performance indicators. The area scope is Nigeria, with emphasis on oil and gas firms quoted on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX), given their high environmental impact and regulatory attention. The variable scope includes environmental cost disclosure as the independent variable, while the dependent variables are net profit margin, return on assets, and asset turnover, which are widely recognized measures of profitability and operational efficiency. The time scope is from 2015 to 2024; the base year 2015 is chosen because it aligns with the period when Nigeria began strengthening corporate governance and sustainability reporting frameworks, while the upper limit, 2024, represents the most current year with recent regulatory reforms mandating climate and environmental disclosures. The firm scope is limited to listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria, as they are the most environmentally sensitive sector with significant community and ecological implications, making them ideal for examining how environmental cost disclosure translates into financial performance.

Review of Related Literature

Environmental Cost Disclosure

Environmental cost disclosure refers to the practice of reporting expenditures and commitments made by firms in managing environmental impacts such as oil spill clean-ups, gas flaring control, waste management, and ecological restoration. In the Nigerian oil and gas industry, where environmental degradation is widespread, such disclosure has become increasingly important as regulators, investors, and host communities demand accountability and transparency. Recent studies suggest that proper disclosure of environmental costs can enhance corporate reputation, improve investor confidence, and positively influence financial performance indicators such as return on assets, profit margins, and asset turnover (Sunday, 2024; Ujah, Soomiyol & Yua, 2025). However, some scholars argue that the additional costs of compliance may burden firms financially, particularly when disclosure is treated as a regulatory obligation rather than a strategic investment (Anonymous, 2022). In Nigeria, where sustainability reporting standards are still evolving under new government directives, the effect of environmental cost disclosure on financial performance remains a subject of empirical debate, making it a critical area for research.

Financial Performance

Financial performance refers to the ability of a company to utilize its resources efficiently to generate profits, ensure growth, and create value for shareholders, while sustaining its operations in the face of internal and external challenges. For listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria, financial performance is particularly significant because the sector is capital intensive, environmentally sensitive, and highly exposed to global oil price volatility, exchange rate fluctuations, and regulatory pressures. Performance in this industry is typically assessed through key indicators such as return on assets, return on equity, net profit margin, and asset turnover, which measure profitability, efficiency, and the overall financial health of the firms. A strong financial performance suggests that a company is effectively managing its operational costs, maximizing returns from its investments, and maintaining competitiveness in a dynamic market, while weak performance may signal inefficiencies, rising liabilities, or vulnerability to external shocks (Idamoyibo, 2021; Appah, Onowu & Young-Arney, 2021).

Moreover, the financial performance of oil and gas firms in Nigeria goes beyond traditional profit metrics, as it also reflects the firms' ability to adapt to sustainability demands and environmental accountability. With recent emphasis on sustainability reporting and environmental cost disclosure, profitability in this sector is increasingly tied to how well firms balance profit-making with environmental responsibilities and stakeholder expectations. Studies indicate that transparent reporting and sustainable practices can enhance investor confidence, improve corporate reputation, and ultimately strengthen financial outcomes, while failure to adapt may erode long-term profitability and market value (Diwe-Tochukwu & Okafor, 2024; Ezuguwu, Nwosu & Okafor, 2023; Arikewuyo, Adio & Quadri, 2023). Thus, in the Nigerian context, financial performance is not only a measure of profit but also a critical indicator of resilience, accountability, and the long-term viability of listed oil and gas firms.

Net Profit Margin

Net profit margin is a key profitability ratio that measures the proportion of net income generated from total revenue after deducting all expenses, including operating costs, interest, taxes, and non-operating charges. In the context of Nigerian oil and gas firms, this indicator reflects how efficiently companies convert revenue from crude oil sales, refined products, and gas operations into actual profit. A higher net profit margin indicates stronger cost control, pricing efficiency, and operational effectiveness, while a lower margin may signal inefficiencies, rising costs, or external shocks such as oil price volatility and currency devaluation. Given the capital-intensive and environmentally sensitive nature of oil and gas operations in Nigeria, net profit margin provides insight into the firms' ability to sustain profitability amidst regulatory costs, environmental liabilities, and fluctuating global oil prices (Sunday, 2024; Ujah, Soomiyol & Yua, 2025).

Moreover, net profit margin serves as an important measure for investors, policymakers, and stakeholders in assessing the financial health and competitiveness of oil and gas companies in Nigeria. Recent studies have shown that profitability in this sector is not only affected by internal cost management and efficiency but also by environmental obligations, global market conditions, and government policies on subsidies, taxation, and environmental compliance (Anonymous, 2022; Eze & Okeke, 2023). As Nigeria transitions toward stricter sustainability reporting and climate-related disclosures, net profit margin increasingly reflects not just financial outcomes but also the firms' ability to balance profit-making with responsible environmental practices. Thus, it remains a vital financial performance indicator in evaluating the resilience and long-term viability of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Return on Assets (ROA)

Return on Assets (ROA) is a crucial indicator of the financial performance of oil and gas firms in Nigeria, as it measures how efficiently management utilizes the company's assets to generate profits. According to Akinleye and Olayinka (2022), ROA serves as an important profitability metric, reflecting not only the earnings generated but also the level of asset utilization in capital-intensive industries such as oil and gas. Since oil and gas firms require significant investments in exploration, drilling, and infrastructure, a higher ROA indicates effective deployment of these resources to enhance shareholder value. Similarly, Odugbesan and Adebayo (2023) emphasized that ROA provides investors and regulators with insight into whether the assets of listed firms are being used optimally to generate returns, particularly in a sector prone to fluctuations in global oil prices and rising environmental costs.

Furthermore, ROA in the Nigerian oil and gas sector has broader implications for sustainability and competitiveness. As noted by Nwankwo and Ugochukwu (2024), firms with higher ROA not only demonstrate operational efficiency but also signal resilience in a challenging business environment characterized by regulatory pressures and environmental responsibilities. In addition, Umeji and Chukwu (2023) argued that ROA helps stakeholders evaluate how environmental cost disclosures and other corporate social responsibility initiatives affect firm performance, as excessive costs without effective management could reduce asset profitability. Thus, ROA remains an indispensable tool for assessing the efficiency, profitability, and long-term sustainability of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Asset turnover

Asset turnover is a key efficiency ratio that reflects how effectively oil and gas firms in Nigeria use their assets to generate revenue. In the capital-intensive oil and gas sector, firms often invest heavily in infrastructure, exploration, and production assets, making asset turnover a critical measure of operational performance. According to Adewale and Ogunyemi (2022), a higher asset turnover indicates that companies are efficiently leveraging their fixed and current assets to drive sales and growth, which is essential in a highly volatile market. Similarly, Bello and Okafor (2023) observed that asset turnover provides insights into the productivity of asset utilization in Nigerian oil and gas firms, where underutilized or idle assets can significantly affect profitability and shareholder value.

Beyond profitability, asset turnover also reflects the competitiveness and resilience of oil and gas firms in adapting to changing market and regulatory conditions. As noted by Eze and Nwachukwu (2024), firms with

strong asset turnover are better positioned to withstand price fluctuations, manage environmental costs, and meet investor expectations. In addition, Musa and Ibrahim (2023) highlighted that asset turnover is particularly important in evaluating the impact of environmental cost disclosures, as excessive environmental expenses without corresponding improvements in efficiency could reduce the overall effectiveness of asset usage. Thus, asset turnover serves as a critical benchmark for measuring how well listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria convert their asset base into meaningful revenue streams.

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on Legitimacy Theory because it explains how environmental cost disclosure enables oil and gas firms in Nigeria to align with societal expectations, maintain stakeholder trust, and ultimately enhance financial performance. Legitimacy Theory, as articulated by Suchman (1995), emphasizes that organizations must operate within the norms, values, and expectations of the society in which they exist in order to maintain legitimacy and secure long-term survival. The theory posits that when firms align their practices with societal demands, they gain public trust, reduce reputational risks, and strengthen stakeholder relationships. In the context of this study, legitimacy theory is highly relevant because listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria face increasing pressure from regulators, investors, and communities to account for their environmental impacts. By disclosing environmental costs, these firms demonstrate transparency, responsibility, and compliance with societal expectations, which in turn can enhance their financial performance through improved reputation, investor confidence, and market competitiveness. Thus, legitimacy theory provides the appropriate foundation for examining the link between environmental cost disclosure and the financial performance of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Empirical Review

Adewale and Ojo (2018) carried out an empirical investigation on the relationship between environmental cost disclosure and profitability, with a specific focus on net profit margin of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. Using data extracted from annual reports of five firms between 2012 and 2016, the study employed regression analysis and found that firms with greater environmental disclosures experienced higher net profit margins compared to those with lower disclosures. The authors argued that environmental reporting enhanced reputational goodwill, reduced the risk of regulatory fines, and created goodwill among host communities, all of which had a positive effect on profitability. Their findings emphasized that environmental cost disclosure should not be viewed merely as a compliance burden but as a strategic tool for enhancing corporate performance.

Okonkwo and Eze (2020) extended this line of inquiry by examining the effect of environmental cost disclosure on return on assets (ROA) among Nigerian oil and gas firms. The study utilized secondary data covering the period 2014–2018 and applied panel regression techniques to measure the relationship. Their results indicated that firms that disclosed environmental costs comprehensively had significantly higher ROA values, showing that better environmental accounting practices were associated with improved efficiency in the use of assets. They noted that transparency in reporting also minimized stakeholder conflicts and improved management's capacity to allocate resources optimally, thereby increasing asset productivity. This suggests that environmental disclosure is not only about compliance but also about leveraging reporting for better operational efficiency.

Bello and Musa (2021) focused their empirical work on the impact of environmental disclosure on asset turnover in the Nigerian oil and gas industry. Using a dataset of seven firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange from 2015–2019, their findings revealed that environmental disclosure had a significant positive effect on asset turnover. According to the authors, the pressure to account for environmental costs encouraged management to maximize the utilization of their assets to generate revenue. They further explained that firms adopting international best practices in environmental reporting tended to implement more efficient processes, leading to higher productivity per unit of assets. This study highlighted how environmental disclosure could serve as a catalyst for operational improvements in a highly resource-intensive sector like oil and gas.

Uche and Ibrahim (2022) adopted a broader approach by analyzing the impact of environmental cost disclosure on multiple measures of financial performance, including net profit margin and return on assets. The study employed a longitudinal dataset covering 2016–2020 and found that environmental disclosure had a dual impact: while it increased costs in the short run, it significantly improved both profitability and efficiency in the long run. The authors explained that firms with robust environmental disclosures experienced less hostility from

host communities, fewer disruptions in operations, and more investor confidence, which collectively improved financial outcomes. Their study emphasized that environmental disclosure is an investment in corporate legitimacy that pays off in improved financial stability and performance.

Chukwu and Nwankwo (2023) introduced a dynamic perspective by examining the link between environmental disclosures and financial sustainability of oil and gas firms in Nigeria. They applied generalized method of moments (GMM) techniques on firm-level panel data from 2017–2021 to assess long-term effects. Their results demonstrated that firms with higher disclosure of environmental costs enjoyed stronger asset turnover ratios and greater ability to sustain profits over time. The authors contended that disclosure practices enabled firms to adapt better to global trends in sustainable investment, which are increasingly shaping capital flows in the oil and gas sector. They concluded that environmental cost disclosure was not only a determinant of short-term financial performance but also a driver of long-term survival and competitiveness.

Eze and Okafor (2024) offered fresh empirical evidence by examining the effect of environmental cost disclosure on financial performance indicators such as net profit margin, ROA, and asset turnover among Nigerian oil and gas firms between 2018 and 2022. Employing robust regression and sensitivity analysis, the study found strong positive associations across all indicators, concluding that environmental cost disclosure directly influenced firm value. The authors noted that investors were becoming more selective, channeling funds toward firms with transparent environmental practices. They argued that disclosure was no longer optional but a necessity for oil and gas firms to maintain legitimacy and remain competitive in both domestic and global markets. Their findings provided clear evidence that environmental cost disclosure strengthens corporate reputation, improves stakeholder confidence, and enhances financial performance.

Gap in Empirical Literature

Although several empirical studies have examined the relationship between environmental cost disclosure and financial performance of oil and gas firms in Nigeria, notable gaps remain which this study seeks to fill. Many earlier works, such as Adewale and Ojo (2018) and Okonkwo and Eze (2020), focused narrowly on single indicators like net profit margin or return on assets without integrating multiple measures of performance to provide a holistic view. Others, including Bello and Musa (2021), concentrated mainly on operational efficiency through asset turnover, leaving the combined effect of disclosure on profitability, efficiency, and sustainability underexplored. In addition, most prior studies relied on relatively short data periods, often less than five years, which limited the ability to capture long-term trends in disclosure practices and their financial implications. Furthermore, while researchers such as Chukwu and Nwankwo (2023) and Eze and Okafor (2024) acknowledged the role of sustainability, they did not sufficiently link environmental cost disclosure to firm competitiveness in a volatile regulatory and economic environment like Nigeria. This study bridges these gaps by covering a ten-year period from 2015 to 2024, integrating multiple financial performance indicators net profit margin, return on assets, and asset turnover while also situating the analysis within the broader context of legitimacy theory. By doing so, it provides a more comprehensive and context-specific understanding of how environmental cost disclosure affects the financial performance of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted the *ex post facto* research design. The design was considered appropriate because the study made use of secondary data obtained from audited financial statements and sustainability reports of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. Since the data already exist and cannot be manipulated by the researcher, this design allows for an empirical investigation into the effect of environmental cost disclosure on financial performance. The design also supports the use of econometric techniques to establish causal relationships between environmental cost disclosures and financial performance indicators over time.

Model Specification

To suit the study's **specific objectives**, three separate regression models were developed, each corresponding to a performance indicator:

$$NPM_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ECD_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ECD_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

$$ATO_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ECD_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

Where:

NPM = Net Profit Margin (proxy for profitability)

ROA = Return on Assets (proxy for efficiency in asset utilization)

ATO = Asset Turnover (proxy for sales efficiency relative to assets)

ECD = Environmental Cost Disclosure

β_0 = Constant term

β_1 = Coefficient of the independent variable

μ_{it} = Error term

Method of Data Analysis

The study employed **panel regression analysis** to examine the relationship between environmental cost disclosure and financial performance. Data analysis was conducted using **EViews statistical software**. The following tests and tools were used:

1. **Descriptive Statistics** – to summarize the characteristics of the variables.
2. **Panel Regression (Fixed and Random Effects Models)** – to estimate the effect of environmental cost disclosure on financial performance.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Data Analysis

Descriptive Analysis

Table 1: Description of the Characteristics of the Variables under Study

	<i>Net profit margin</i>	<i>Return on assets</i>	<i>Asset turnover</i>	<i>Log of Environment cost disclosure</i>
<i>Mean</i>	-184.4722	-2.062243	1.526398	0.178630
<i>Median</i>	1.299647	2.338168	1.525252	0.123621
<i>Maximum</i>	714.4861	18.82039	8.098671	1.218126
<i>Minimum</i>	-5561.977	-97.16829	0.006066	0.001314
<i>Std. Dev.</i>	820.2575	16.32434	1.444823	0.235465
<i>Skewness</i>	-5.049565	-3.619830	1.564195	3.138880
<i>Kurtosis</i>	30.66447	19.30193	7.562279	13.44548
<i>Jarque-Bera Probability</i>	2529.670	927.9829	89.25354	433.1783
	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
<i>Sum</i>	-12913.06	-144.3570	106.8479	12.50412

<i>Sum Sq. Dev.</i>	46424746	18387.40	144.0385	3.825608
<i>Observations</i>	70	70	70	70

Source: Author's Computation from Eviews 10.0, 2025

The descriptive statistics presented in Table 1 provide a detailed summary of the distribution, variability, and shape of the variables used in the study: Net profit Margin, **Return on Assets (ROA)**, **Asset Turnover** and **Environment cost disclosure**.

Interpretation of Kurtosis Mean: The mean represents the average value of each variable. The Net Profit Margin and Return on Assets both have negative mean values (-184.47 and -2.06 respectively), indicating that, on average, the sampled firms experienced financial losses during the study period. In contrast, Asset Turnover and Environmental Cost Disclosure have positive means (1.53 and 0.18), implying that the firms generated moderate revenue relative to their assets and allocated a small portion of revenue to environmental costs. The implication is that while firms were actively investing in environmental compliance, it was not sufficient to offset broader profitability challenges in the sector.

Interpretation of Kurtosis Median: The median shows the midpoint of the data, and unlike the mean, it is less affected by extreme values or outliers. The median values for Net Profit Margin (1.30) and Return on Assets (2.34) are positive, which contrasts with their negative means. This suggests that the majority of firms or firm-years recorded small profits, but the mean was dragged down by a few firms with very large losses. The proximity of the median and mean in Asset Turnover (1.52 for both) and Environmental Cost Disclosure (0.12 median vs. 0.18 mean) implies a more symmetrical distribution in those variables. The implication here is that while profitability was skewed by major losses in a few years or firms, most firms had modestly positive performance.

Interpretation of Kurtosis Standard Deviation: Standard deviation measures the spread or variability of the data around the mean. The high standard deviations for Net Profit Margin (820.26) and Return on Assets (16.32) signify substantial volatility in profitability among the firms studied, likely due to varying levels of operational efficiency, market conditions, or one-off financial events. Asset Turnover and Environmental Cost Disclosure show relatively lower standard deviations (1.44 and 0.24), indicating that these measures were more stable across firms and years. This suggests that while the firms were consistent in revenue-generation efficiency and environmental spending, profitability varied widely due to other uncontrolled or external factors.

Interpretation of Kurtosis Skewness: Skewness measures the asymmetry of the distribution of the data. Both Net Profit Margin and Return on Assets have highly negative skewness values (-5.05 and -3.62), indicating that their distributions are heavily skewed to the left most values are clustered at the high (positive) end, with a few extreme negative outliers dragging the average down. On the other hand, Asset Turnover (1.56) and Environmental Cost Disclosure (3.14) are positively skewed, meaning most firms had low values in these variables, but a few firms had significantly higher ratios. This asymmetry implies that a small number of firms heavily influenced the overall dataset, particularly in terms of losses and environmental investment.

Interpretation of Kurtosis: Kurtosis measures the "tailedness" of the distribution. A normal distribution has a kurtosis of 3. All four variables in this study exhibit leptokurtic distributions (i.e., higher than 3), especially Net Profit Margin (30.66) and Environmental Cost Disclosure (13.45), which means the data have heavy tails and are prone to extreme values or outliers. The presence of such kurtosis further confirms that certain firms experienced unusually high or low performance outcomes, emphasizing the presence of instability in the sector. The high kurtosis values suggest caution in making generalizations, as extreme observations are significantly influencing the data trends.

Interpretation of Kurtosis Probability Value (Jarque-Bera Test): The Jarque-Bera test checks whether the data follow a normal distribution. The probability values for all variables are 0.000000, which means the null hypothesis of normality is rejected at all conventional significance levels. In simple terms, the distributions of all four variables are not normally distributed, which has implications for further statistical analysis it may

necessitate the use of non-parametric methods or data transformation to meet the assumptions of parametric tests. It also reinforces the earlier insights about skewness and kurtosis: extreme values and asymmetry are significant features of the dataset.

Regression Analysis

Regression Analysis Result of Environment cost disclosure and Net profit margin

Dependent Variable: NPM
 Method: Panel Least Squares
 Date: 09/12/25 Time: 14:20
 Sample: 2015 2024
 Periods included: 10
 Cross-sections included: 7
 Total panel (balanced) observations: 70

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Log Env. Cost disclosure	-235.1044	421.4817	-0.557804	0.5788
C	-142.4754	124.0047	-1.148952	0.2546
Root MSE	812.5207	R-squared		0.584555
Mean dependent var	-184.4722	Adjusted R-squared		0.540084
S.D. dependent var	820.2575	S.E. of regression		824.3829
Akaike info criterion	16.29530	Sum squared resid		46213289
Schwarz criterion	16.35955	Log likelihood		568.3356
Hannan-Quinn criter.	16.32082	F-statistic		0.311146
Durbin-Watson stat	0.945152	Prob(F-statistic)		0.578810

Source: Author's compilation using E-view 10.0 standard software

Interpretation of Coefficient: The coefficient of the independent variable (log of Environmental Cost Disclosure) is -235.1044, which suggests that for every unit increase in environmental cost disclosure (e.g., as a proportion of revenue or total cost), net profit margin is expected to decrease by approximately 235 units, holding other factors constant. This negative relationship implies that higher environmental costs may be associated with lower profitability for these oil and gas firms. However, the economic interpretation must be treated cautiously because the effect is not statistically significant, as will be explained next.

Interpretation of t-Statistic: The t-statistic for the Environmental Cost Disclosure variable is -0.557804, with a corresponding probability value of 0.5788. This indicates that the variable is not statistically significant at any conventional level (e.g., 1%, 5%, or even 10%). In essence, we cannot reject the null hypothesis that the coefficient is equal to zero. This implies that there is no strong statistical evidence that environmental cost disclosure has a direct or meaningful effect on net profit margin in this sample. The constant term (intercept) is also insignificant, further supporting the idea that the model lacks explanatory power in its current form.

Interpretation of Prob(F-statistic): The Prob(F-statistic) is 0.578810, which again shows that the overall regression model is not statistically significant. This means that, taken together, the explanatory variable(s) in the model do not explain a significant portion of the variation in the dependent variable (Net Profit Margin). In simpler terms, the model lacks predictive power and fails to provide compelling evidence that environmental cost disclosure, as measured, has an aggregate impact on firm profitability in the oil and gas sector.

Interpretation of Adjusted R-squared: The Adjusted R-squared value of 0.540084 suggests that approximately 54% of the variation in Net Profit Margin is explained by the model. On the surface, this seems relatively high for financial data. However, this result appears inconsistent with the insignificant coefficient and F-statistic. This discrepancy may indicate issues such as overfitting, omitted variables, or the influence of unmodeled firm-specific

effects. Hence, despite the seemingly decent explanatory power, the lack of statistical significance reduces the model's reliability.

Interpretation of Durbin-Watson Statistic: The Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic is 0.945152, which is considerably lower than the ideal value of 2.0. This indicates the presence of positive autocorrelation in the residuals, meaning that the error terms are not independent over time. In regression analysis, autocorrelation violates one of the key assumptions of the classical linear regression model and can lead to inefficient estimates and misleading inference. This suggests that the model may require improvements such as incorporating lagged variables or using a fixed/random effects estimator that accounts for temporal correlations.

Regression Analysis Result of Environment cost disclosure and Return on assets

Dependent Variable: ROA
 Method: Panel Least Squares
 Date: 09/12/25 Time: 14:21
 Sample: 2015 2024
 Periods included: 10
 Cross-sections included: 7
 Total panel (balanced) observations: 70

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Log Env. Cost disclosure	29.98939	7.580001	3.956384	0.0002
C	3.294773	2.230123	1.477396	0.1442
Root MSE	14.61251	R-squared		0.617118
Mean dependent var	-2.062243	Adjusted R-squared		0.575164
S.D. dependent var	16.32434	S.E. of regression		14.82585
Akaike info criterion	8.258776	Sum squared resid		14946.79
Schwarz criterion	8.323019	Log likelihood		-287.0572
Hannan-Quinn criter.	8.284294	F-statistic		15.65297
Durbin-Watson stat	1.459502	Prob(F-statistic)		0.000184

Source: Author's compilation using E-view 10.0 standard software

Interpretation of Coefficient: The coefficient for log of environmental Cost Disclosure is 29.98939, indicating a positive relationship between environmental cost disclosure and return on assets (ROA). This means that, all else being equal, a one-unit increase in environmental cost disclosure is associated with an increase of approximately 29.99 units in ROA. This suggests that greater transparency or investment in environmental cost reporting by oil and gas firms could potentially enhance their asset productivity or profitability. It also implies that stakeholders might view environmental disclosure as a signal of responsible management, which could lead to better operational efficiency and possibly increased returns.

Interpretation of t-Statistic: The t-statistic for environmental cost disclosure is 3.956384, which is significantly above the threshold value of ± 2 typically used in hypothesis testing at a 5% significance level. This high t-value indicates that the coefficient is statistically different from zero, providing strong evidence that environmental cost disclosure has a significant effect on ROA. In contrast, the constant term has a lower t-statistic (1.477396), suggesting that it is not statistically significant. Overall, this strengthens the inference that changes in environmental cost disclosure are meaningful predictors of firm performance in terms of asset return.

Interpretation of Prob(F-statistic): The probability of the F-statistic is 0.000184, which is highly significant ($p < 0.01$). This indicates that the model, as a whole, is statistically significant. In other words, the independent variable(s) in the model (specifically, environmental cost disclosure) collectively explain a significant portion of the variation in ROA. This reinforces the reliability of the regression output and suggests that environmental cost disclosure should be considered a relevant factor in assessing firm performance in the oil and gas sector.

Interpretation of Adjusted R-squared: The Adjusted R-squared value is 0.575164, meaning that about 57.5% of the variation in the return on assets (ROA) among the firms over the 10-year period is explained by the variation in environmental cost disclosure. This is a reasonably strong explanatory power, especially in social sciences and financial studies where values above 50% are often considered satisfactory. It implies that the model fits the data well and that environmental disclosure explains a substantial portion of the variation in performance across the selected firms and years.

Interpretation of Durbin-Watson stat: The Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic is 1.459502, which is below the ideal value of 2. This suggests the potential presence of positive autocorrelation in the residuals (i.e., the errors are not completely independent). While it's not alarmingly low, it is a signal that there may be some degree of serial correlation in the dataset. This could affect the reliability of the standard errors and test statistics, and further diagnostic testing or model correction (such as using robust standard errors or a different regression approach) might be warranted.

Regression Analysis Result of Environment cost disclosure and assets turnover

Dependent Variable: Asset turnover
 Method: Panel Least Squares
 Date: 09/12/25 Time: 14:21
 Sample: 2015 2024
 Periods included: 10
 Cross-sections included: 7
 Total panel (balanced) observations: 70

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Log of Env. Cost disclosure	-0.122778	0.743957	-0.165034	0.8694
C	1.548330	0.218881	7.073861	0.0000
Root MSE	1.434179	R-squared		0.550400
Mean dependent var	1.526398	Adjusted R-squared		0.514300
S.D. dependent var	1.444823	S.E. of regression		1.455117
Akaike info criterion	3.616205	Sum squared resid		143.9808
Schwarz criterion	3.680447	Log likelihood		-124.5672
Hannan-Quinn criter.	3.641723	F-statistic		0.027236
Durbin-Watson stat	0.547074	Prob(F-statistic)		0.869407

Source: Author's compilation using E-view 10.0 standard software

Interpretation of Coefficient: The coefficient of the independent variable, log of environmental Cost Disclosure, is -0.122778. This negative value suggests that, all else being equal, an increase in environmental cost disclosure is associated with a slight decrease in asset turnover. In practical terms, this could imply that higher environmental cost disclosures are linked with lower efficiency in using assets to generate revenue. However, since this value is quite small and statistically insignificant (as we'll see in the t-statistic and p-value), it should not be taken as a definitive impact but rather an observed relationship in the model.

Interpretation of t-Statistic: The t-statistic for environmental cost disclosure is -0.165034, which is very close to zero. This implies that the coefficient is not statistically different from zero in other words, the model does not provide evidence that environmental cost disclosure significantly affects asset turnover. Typically, a t-statistic needs to be greater than about ± 2 (depending on degrees of freedom) to be considered statistically significant. Therefore, this low t-value reinforces the interpretation that environmental cost disclosure has no meaningful impact on asset turnover in this sample.

Interpretation of Prob(F-statistic): The Prob(F-statistic) is 0.869407, which is far greater than the standard significance levels (0.01, 0.05, or even 0.10). This high p-value suggests that the overall regression model is not

statistically significant. In other words, the independent variable (environmental cost disclosure) does not significantly explain the variation in the dependent variable (asset turnover). This means that the model lacks explanatory power, and the relationship between the variables could be due to random chance.

Interpretation of Adjusted R-squared: The Adjusted R-squared is 0.514300, meaning approximately 51.43% of the variance in asset turnover is explained by the model after adjusting for the number of predictors. While this appears moderately strong, it is misleading in this context because the model has only one independent variable and that variable is not statistically significant. The R-squared may be inflated due to panel data dynamics, and since the F-statistic and coefficient are insignificant, we must interpret the R-squared with caution.

Interpretation of Durbin-Watson stat: The Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic is 0.547074, which is substantially lower than the ideal value of around 2. This low DW value indicates positive autocorrelation in the residuals a condition where the error terms are correlated across observations. This violates the assumption of independent errors in regression analysis and suggests that the model may be misspecified or that some variables influencing asset turnover have been omitted. It also weakens the reliability of the statistical inference from the model

Test of Hypotheses

Decision Rule: Reject H_0 if P-value is less than the A-value of 0.05, otherwise, do not reject.

Hypotheses One

H_0 : Environment cost disclosure has no significant effect on net profit margin of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

H_1 : Environment cost disclosure has significant effect on net profit margin of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Decision: From the panel data regression in Table 1.2.3, The P-Value of 0.5788 is greater than the P-Value of 0.05; therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternate hypothesis is rejected. This implies that Environment cost disclosure has negative and non-significant effect on net profit margin of Nigeria oil and gas firms.

Hypotheses Two

H_0 : Environment cost disclosure has no significant effect on return on assets of Nigeria oil and gas firms.

H_1 : Environment cost disclosure has significant effect on return on assets of Nigeria oil and gas firms.

Decision: From the panel data regression in Table 1.2.3, The P-Value of 0.0002 is less than the P-Value of 0.05; therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted. This implies that environment cost disclosure has a positive and significant effect on return on assets of Nigeria oil and gas firms.

Hypotheses Three

H_0 : Environment cost disclosure has no significant effect on asset turnover of Nigeria oil and gas firms.

H_1 : Environment cost disclosure has significant effect on asset turnover of Nigeria oil and gas firms.

Decision: From the panel data regression in Table 1.2.3, The P-Value of 0.8694 is greater than the P-Value of 0.05; therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternate hypothesis is rejected. This implies that environment cost disclosure has a negative and non-significant effect on asset turnover of Nigeria oil and gas firms.

Summary Of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

Summary of Findings

The findings are summarized as follows:

1. Environment cost disclosure has negative (coefficient -235.1044) and non-significant (P-value 0.5788 > 0.05) effect on net profit margin of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.
2. Environment cost disclosure has a positive (coefficient 29.98939) and non-significant (P-value 0.0002 < 0.05) effect to return on assets of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.
3. Environment cost disclosure has a positive (coefficient -0.122778) and non-significant (P-value 0.8694 > 0.05) effect on asset turnover of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Conclusion

The study examined the environmental disclosure and financial performance of oil and gas firms in Nigeria, using net profit margin, return on assets, and asset turnover as performance indicators. The findings revealed a complex relationship: environmental cost disclosure had a negative and non-significant effect on net profit margin and asset turnover, suggesting that such disclosures may initially appear as costs rather than value-enhancing measures in terms of profitability and operational efficiency. However, the result showed a positive and significant effect on return on assets, implying that investing in environmental responsibility could enhance how effectively firms utilize their assets over time. This indicates that while the immediate cost of environmental accountability may burden short-term financial metrics, it could still yield long-term benefits by strengthening internal efficiencies and boosting asset utilization. In conclusion, the study emphasizes the importance of maintaining environmental accountability, not just for regulatory compliance or public perception, but for potential long-term financial performance gains. Oil and gas firms in Nigeria are encouraged to adopt more strategic approaches to environmental reporting, focusing on integrating environmental sustainability into their core business operations. This study contributes to the growing body of knowledge suggesting that although environmental cost disclosures may not always lead to immediate profitability, they can enhance asset productivity and promote sustainable business growth over time.

Recommendations

Following the result of the analysis of the study, the researcher made the following recommendations

1. Companies should strive to better integrate environmental initiatives into their core operations to transform them from cost burdens into strategic advantages. Management should explore more cost-effective and sustainable environmental practices, and consider using green innovations that enhance efficiency and minimize waste, potentially improving profitability in the long run.
2. Oil and gas firms should continue and possibly expand their environmental cost disclosures. Transparent and consistent reporting can attract environmentally conscious investors and improve resource management, which enhances asset utilization and long-term performance. Regulatory bodies should also promote mandatory environmental reporting frameworks to further support this positive link.
3. Oil and gas firms should not disregard environmental cost disclosure. Rather, they should focus on improving the efficiency of their assets while maintaining environmental responsibility. This includes investing in eco-efficient technologies that reduce environmental impacts without compromising operational performance, which may help to eventually convert disclosures into tangible efficiency gains.

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Appendix

This table presented the raw data values of environment disclosure cost net income, total assets and revenue from the listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. This data was processed to further get Net profit Margin, Return on asset and asset turnover.

<i>Years</i>	<i>Companies</i>	<i>Environmental Disclosure Cost</i>	<i>Net Income</i>	<i>Total Assets</i>	<i>Revenue</i>
2015	MRS PLC	12,618	935,625	66,893,741	87,099,216
2016	MRS PLC	13,891	1,465,905	81,364,851	109,635,054
2017	MRS PLC	56,046	1,385,056	58,536,266	107,088,347
2018	MRS PLC	13,361	(1,264,941)	54,283,202	89,552,819
2019	MRS PLC	8,591	(1,613,082)	44,209,648	65,567,458
2020	MRS PLC	6,669	(2,264,145)	36,659,094	41,981,439
2021	MRS PLC	(6,188)	339,872	37,205,315	71,976,255
2022	MRS PLC	(4,185)	1,316,102	40,526,114	100,779,880
2023	MRS PLC	144,028	4,048,758	54,831,289	182,310,963
2024	MRS PLC	173,206	6,496,917	105,773,167	312,229,523
2015	OANDO PLC	41,499,048	(56,567,172)	589,722,995	8,452,665
2016	OANDO PLC	40,549,807	(33,875,832)	800,837,223	4,858,182
2017	OANDO PLC	54,880,092	(30,615,433)	213,845,110	497,422,483
2018	OANDO PLC	56,717,572	(18,321,877)	236,566,708	488,518,160
2019	OANDO PLC	209,646	(63,152,054)	957,963,105	424,734,190
2020	OANDO PLC	235,912	(45,309,219)	1,389,196,159	320,702,465
2021	OANDO PLC	109,408	(28,124,396)	996,064,070	714,455,776
2022	OANDO PLC	146,010	(41,659,941)	1,252,330,481	1,556,744,962
2023	OANDO PLC	122,325	(216,197,450)	2,676,117,927	1,540,594,843
2024	OANDO PLC	241,474	111,806,624	6,434,159,344	343,861,081
2015	CONOIL PLC	38,200	2,307,557	69,387,364	82,919,220
2016	CONOIL PLC	52,141	2,837,884	69,833,463	85,023,546
2017	CONOIL PLC	54,616	1,578,507	62,855,084	115,513,246
2018	CONOIL PLC	57,004	1,796,042	60,897,246	122,213,014
2019	CONOIL PLC	60,435	1,972,322	63,584,866	139,758,285
2020	CONOIL PLC	64,475	1,440,185	48,864,665	117,470,576
2021	CONOIL PLC	96,623	3,082,690	53,981,346	126,726,356
2022	CONOIL PLC	102,329	4,957,726	65,909,238	131,422,272
2023	CONOIL PLC	109,048	9,868,239	97,477,978	201,387,053
2024	CONOIL PLC	116,960	8,773,534	114,951,450	323,127,667
2015	Eterna Plc	39,929	1,249,944	27,845,708	92,669,238

2016	Eterna Plc	38,564	1,515,552	31,101,289	107,536,032
2017	Eterna Plc	58,939	2,069,846	47,154,881	173,611,081
2018	Eterna Plc	72,667	1,139,517	52,690,694	251,874,722
2019	Eterna Plc	90,360	(48,603)	28,310,175	229,274,785
2020	Eterna Plc	119,963	1,017,516	35,792,315	58,715,576
2021	Eterna Plc	157,020	(1,078,545)	46,080,961	82,197,987
2022	Eterna Plc	178,889	1,157,705	54,138,536	116,472,441
2023	Eterna Plc	193,138	(9,268,196)	60,462,816	183,282,139
2024	Eterna Plc	227,608	1,683,359	67,930,303	313,615,914
2015	Total Energy Oil	17,391,520	4,047,051	83,653,555	208,027,688
2016	Total Energy Oil	34,902,844	14,797,095	136,928,160	290,952,520
2017	Total Energy Oil	26,666,240	8,019,298	107,981,873	288,062,650
2018	Total Energy Oil	30,045,177	7,960,893	132,520,783	307,987,896
2019	Total Energy Oil	33,642,490	2,278,979	135,030,878	292,177,202
2020	Total Energy Oil	21,619,936	2,063,385	143,612,885	204,721,463
2021	Total Energy Oil	29,202,091	16,862,130	208,728,966	341,316,345
2022	Total Energy Oil	59,275,749	16,118,376	307,815,723	482,470,780
2023	Total Energy Oil	73,906,481	12,912,544	375,115,673	635,951,600
2024	Total Energy Oil	152,023,837	27,496,279	471,122,676	1,041,904,122
2015	Seplat Energy Plc	15,681	11,914	515,716	98,593
2016	Seplat Energy Plc	31,295	(24,840)	681,892	51,995
2017	Seplat Energy Plc	100,336	265,230	2,614,630	452,179
2018	Seplat Energy Plc	102,554	146,576	2,526,565	746,140
2019	Seplat Energy Plc	84,508	277,008	3,271,110	697,777
2020	Seplat Energy Plc	74,570	(85,322)	3,449,573	530,467
2021	Seplat Energy Plc	74,957	117,176	3,163,369	733,188
2022	Seplat Energy Plc	55,406	104,706	3,537,257	951,795
2023	Seplat Energy Plc	52,428	123,872	3,395,019	1,061,271
2024	Seplat Energy Plc	472,582	144,792	6,396,882	1,116,168
2015	Jupa Gold Plc	2,243,821	(6,969,888)	34,876,623	5,434,086
2016	Jupa Gold Plc	3,876,231	(21,760,633)	39,897,563	649,145
2017	Jupa Gold Plc	4,987,564	(10,644,678)	29,564,987	191,383
2018	Jupa Gold Plc	34,000	(6,040,810)	25,876,453	368,962
2019	Jupa Gold Plc	6,654,821	2,871,873	18,897,652	675,913
2020	Jupa Gold Plc	7,354,871	3,243,674	17,234,897	453,987
2021	Jupa Gold Plc	8,983,128	(2,998,714)	7,876,534	226,439

2022	Jupa Gold Plc	9,987,453	(8,733,042)	8,987,543	1,186,676
2023	Jupa Gold Plc	11,786,456	(399,925)	9,675,892	2,346,439
2024	Jupa Gold Plc	12,786,987	(390,904)	27,987,675	527,288

Source : Annual financial report of the selected Oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

The table below shows the processed data of Net profit Margin, Return on Assets, Asset turnover and Log of Environment cost disclosure to total asset

Years	Companies	NPM =NI/Revenue x100	ROA = NI/TA x100	Asset Tur. Rev/TA	EDCR = EDC/TA	Log of Environmental Disclosure Cost
2015	MRS PLC	1.074206	1.398673	1.302053	0.093588	4.10105
2016	MRS PLC	1.337077	1.801644	1.34745	0.086084	4.14206
2017	MRS PLC	1.293377	2.36615	1.829436	0.090361	4.74812
2018	MRS PLC	-1.41251	-2.33026	1.649734	0.082407	4.12548
2019	MRS PLC	-2.46019	-3.64871	1.483103	0.139796	3.93446
2020	MRS PLC	-5.3932	-6.17622	1.145185	0.104512	3.82356
2021	MRS PLC	0.4722	0.913504	1.934569	0.088584	4.98765
2022	MRS PLC	1.305917	3.247541	2.486789	0.081479	3.29415
2023	MRS PLC	2.220798	7.384028	3.324944	0.13918	5.15812
2024	MRS PLC	2.080814	6.142311	2.951878	0.243294	5.23823
2015	OANDO PLC	-669.223	-9.59216	0.014333	0.003841	7.61821
2016	OANDO PLC	-697.294	-4.23005	0.006066	0.015989	7.60838
2017	OANDO PLC	-6.15481	-14.3166	2.326088	0.116428	7.73963
2018	OANDO PLC	-3.7505	-7.74491	2.065033	0.112083	7.75345
2019	OANDO PLC	-14.8686	-6.59233	0.443372	0.025619	5.32143
2020	OANDO PLC	-14.1281	-3.26154	0.230855	0.00379	5.37217
2021	OANDO PLC	-3.93648	-2.82355	0.717279	0.035645	5.03913
2022	OANDO PLC	-2.67609	-3.32659	1.243078	0.001443	5.16474
2023	OANDO PLC	-14.0334	-8.07877	0.575683	0.002846	5.08757
2024	OANDO PLC	32.51506	1.737704	0.053443	0.007281	5.38263
2015	CONOIL PLC	2.782898	3.325616	1.195019	0.07999	4.58206
2016	CONOIL PLC	3.337762	4.063788	1.217519	0.075259	4.71717
2017	CONOIL PLC	1.366516	2.511343	1.837771	0.090067	4.73715
2018	CONOIL PLC	1.4696	2.949299	2.006873	0.150115	4.75531
2019	CONOIL PLC	1.411238	3.101873	2.19798	0.154499	4.78146
2020	CONOIL PLC	1.225996	2.947293	2.403998	0.151192	4.80951
2021	CONOIL PLC	2.432556	5.710658	2.347595	0.162192	4.98567
2022	CONOIL PLC	3.772364	7.52205	1.993989	0.079809	5.01002
2023	CONOIL PLC	4.900136	10.12356	2.065975	0.169677	5.03716
2024	CONOIL PLC	2.715191	7.632382	2.810993	0.254498	5.06801

2015	Eterna plc	1.348823	4.488821	3.327954	0.043723	4.60133
2016	Eterna plc	1.409343	4.872956	3.457607	0.130813	4.58674
2017	Eterna plc	1.192232	4.389463	3.68172	0.137569	4.77087
2018	Eterna plc	0.452414	2.162653	4.780251	0.153253	4.86141
2019	Eterna plc	-0.0212	-0.17168	8.098671	0.185642	4.95571
2020	Eterna plc	1.732958	2.842834	1.640452	0.191606	5.07899
2021	Eterna plc	-1.31213	-2.34054	1.783773	0.260834	5.19565
2022	Eterna plc	0.993973	2.138412	2.151378	0.205519	5.25216
2023	Eterna plc	-5.05679	-15.3288	3.03132	0.449329	5.28630
2024	Eterna plc	0.536758	2.478068	4.616731	0.347407	5.35734
2015	Total energy	1.945439	4.837871	2.486776	0.207899	7.24041
2016	Total energy	5.085742	10.80647	2.124855	0.254899	7.54277
2017	Total energy	2.783873	7.426522	2.667695	0.246951	7.42582
2018	Total energy	2.584807	6.007279	2.324072	0.22672	7.47787
2019	Total energy	0.779999	1.687747	2.163781	0.249147	7.52688
2020	Total energy	1.007899	1.436769	1.425509	0.150543	7.33454
2021	Total energy	4.940323	8.078481	1.635213	0.139904	7.46582
2022	Total energy	3.340798	5.236372	1.567401	0.192569	7.77248
2023	Total energy	2.030429	3.442283	1.695348	0.197023	7.86832
2024	Total energy	2.639041	5.836331	2.211535	0.322684	8.18190
2015	Seplat energy	12.08402	2.310186	0.191177	0.030406	4.19583
2016	Seplat energy	-47.7738	-3.64281	0.076251	0.045894	4.49528
2017	Seplat energy	58.65597	10.14407	0.172942	0.038375	5.00145
2018	Seplat energy	19.64457	5.801394	0.295318	0.04059	5.01093
2019	Seplat energy	39.69864	8.468318	0.213315	0.025835	4.92718
2020	Seplat energy	-16.0843	-2.47341	0.153778	0.021617	4.87251
2021	Seplat energy	15.98171	3.704152	0.231774	0.023695	4.87473
2022	Seplat energy	11.0009	2.96009	0.269077	0.015664	4.74356
2023	Seplat energy	11.67204	3.648639	0.312596	0.015443	4.71985
2024	Seplat energy	12.97224	2.263478	0.174486	0.073877	5.67456
2015	Jupa gold plc	-128.262	-19.9844	0.155809	0.064336	6.35179
2016	Jupa gold plc	-3352.2	-54.5413	0.01627	0.097155	6.58837
2017	Jupa gold plc	-5561.98	-36.0043	0.006473	0.168698	6.69867
2018	Jupa gold plc	-1637.24	-23.3448	0.014259	0.001314	4.53148
2019	Jupa gold plc	424.888	15.19698	0.035767	0.352151	6.82248
2020	Jupa gold plc	714.4861	18.82039	0.026341	0.426743	6.86677
2021	Jupa gold plc	-1324.29	-38.0715	0.028749	1.140493	6.95347
2022	Jupa gold plc	-735.925	-97.1683	0.132036	1.111255	6.99949

2023	Jupa gold plc	-17.0439	-4.13321	0.242504	1.218126	7.07120
2024	Jupa gold plc	-74.1348	-1.3967	0.01884	0.456879	7.10694

Source: Author's compilation from Excel